

Impulse Measured Momentum and Internal Time and Spatial Co-ordinates

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If one considers a particle with rest mass, then it has a momentum if it is moving (i.e. there is a speed/velocity). This momentum may be measured in a number of different ways. For instance, if one is in a moving frame and the particle is at rest in the lab frame, then in the moving frame one may use a clock together with light to bounce it off the particle at different times. One needs to know c , the speed of light and the equation $x=ct$, but does not need a ruler. (At one time, however, a ruler was needed to establish $x=ct$.) Alternatively, one may use a ruler and clock as well as photons to measure v . Finally, one may analyze an impulse hit which requires no clock or ruler. In particular, for a photon one does not measure speed when measuring momentum.

We suggest that momentum is a relative property of the object as it is frame dependent, but that it requires motion and that this sense of motion should be able to be sensed by the particle itself because no external measurement is required in the impulse hit measurement scenario. For example, a particle with rest mass moving with speed v will create a certain impulse on a target. This is property of the particle and its frame, but the particle should also be linked with an intrinsic set of ruler and time gradations because these too should be internal giving rise to the sense of velocity/speed. There cannot be momentum without v and so the sense of this v should exist at every instant (considering time resolution) and should not emerge after some measurement. Given that different momenta may correspond to different energies, one must have a built-in $x-t$ ruler-clock system, we argue, in order that the notion of speed to make sense. We argue that speed is an intrinsic property (linked to a frame of reference) and does not emerge simply because one has a ruler and clock which may be used to take measurements. The question then becomes to determine how the clock and ruler gradations are created, which we mention briefly as we have discussed this in previous notes.

We further note that the work/effort that goes into creating energy, momentum is manifest in increased order (loss of entropy) of the intrinsic space-time of a free particle.

Particle with Rest Mass

A particle with rest mass has a momentum proportional to v (velocity) which usually requires a ruler and clock for its measurement. This, in turn, implies that ruler and clock gradations must exist. For example, one may use light in classical mechanics together with a ruler and clock to measure speed. Alternatively, one may use a clock and $x=vt$, but this latter equation required a ruler at one point for it to be experimentally verified. Thus, the notion of ruler and clock gradations seems to be required for the sense of velocity and hence momentum of a particle with rest mass to exist. We also note that a frame of reference is also a consideration because one sees a particle velocity in a certain frame.

If one considers one frame and a particle has a certain momentum in this frame, then one may measure this momentum by its impulse impact. For example, one may create a set of weak resistance layers, one on top of the other, and count how many are broken in an impulse hit. This gives a sense of momentum and if one knows rest mass, one may find velocity without any

clock or ruler. Yet at the same time, momentum cannot exist without motion which requires a ruler gradation and clock interval to make sense.

If a particle is moving in free space, then no such external ruler or clock may exist, yet we argue that an internal sense of dynamics should. From special relativity, $p/E = v/c$ for a particle with rest mass so the dynamic property variables (dependent on the frame of reference) p (momentum) and energy define the particle, but also its motion v . Motion v , however, cannot exist without ruler gradations and a clock interval. We suggest that p and E should be linked to these gradations and intervals. In a sense, p and E which seem to be independent of v given that E was created through work and p represents impulse define v and hence a ruler and clock system as well, we argue, for consistency.

This is unusual in that this ruler and clock interval system depend specifically on the dynamic properties E and p of a particle in question. In other words, different particles (with rest mass) have different ruler and clock intervals. This is fine, however, as the sense of velocity depends on these variables and so there is no a priori reason to believe that the gradations of the ruler and clock should be universal. One may introduce a universal ruler and clock, but each free particle has its own clock and ruler gradations based on E and p regardless of the universal ruler (which is used in classical mechanics).

Explicitly Creating the Ruler and Clock Gradations

The next issue is to explicitly create the clock and ruler gradations and this has been discussed in previous notes. In particular, it has been suggested that the function $\exp(ibx)$ allows for the periodic creation of constant/ b intervals with equal weight for the x points within the gradation, i.e. bx is a linear variable. Given that b is a conserved quantity, $\exp(ib_1x)\exp(ib_2x)=\exp(i(b_1+b_2)x)$ and that p is the only guaranteed dynamic quantity, we suggest $b=p$ (or $p \cdot r$ for the more general case).

Alternatively, we have suggested using the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$ and noting that it has degenerate points for $x = x_0 + \text{constant}/p$ and $t=t_0 + \text{constant}/E$. In this case, one has to create the ruler and clock gradations which makes sense as E and p define the properties of the particle. This constant may be multiplied by an integer.

The Idea of Order or Entropy

A curious result which appears is that E and p , by governing the ruler and clock gradations, also associate the order/resolution or entropy linked with these. In other words, creating a high E and a high p suggest high time and spatial resolution and low entropy. In classical mechanics, there is no such notion, it seems. In other words, effort is required to create both E and p and this effort does not just appear in high values of E and p , but in order in time and space. In other words, energy and momentum are in a sense creating the order of space time. If there is more of both, there is sharper time and spatial resolution (order).

The Photon

In the case of the photon, there is also an E and p and so the above ideas should hold for consistency because a photon also has the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$. Thus, even though c (in a vacuum) is independent of p , there is motion linked with p and the same degeneracy in $-Et+px$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that because p (which requires motion and is frame dependent both for a particle with rest mass and without, i.e. photon) can be measured without the use of any clock or ruler through analysis of an impulse collision, the sense of motion must be carried internally by the particle. For example, for a particle with rest mass, $v= p/E$ ($c=1$) and for a photon, $c=E/p$. In other words, p and E completely define speed, but speed depends on gradations in space and time and so E and p should define these as well. We have argued previously that this can be seen through degenerate points in the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$, i.e. $x_0 + \text{constant}/p$, $t_0 + \text{constant}/E$ where the constant can change in an integer manner, i.e. $\text{constant} = A * n$ where n is an integer.

This means that intervals of time and space are linked to p and E and are not universal. This suggests that the work/effort which goes into creating E and p also creates order or sharp resolution in space and time.